

Entrepreneurial Prospects of Poultry Layer Farming in Bangladesh: A Stochastic Frontier Analysis

Md. Mahmudul Hassan*

The present study analyzes the Technical Efficiency (TE) of poultry layer production in Bangladesh for a sample of 100 poultry farmers selected from Kishoreganj and Dhaka districts in Bangladesh. Stochastic parametric practice is employed to evaluate the TE of the sample poultry farmers. The results show that size of Day Old Chicks (DOC) and feed input played a crucial role in egg output. Estimated mean TE was 34%, 48% and 61% for layer small, medium and large farm respectively and this variation proposes the existence of further opportunities for layer farmers in sample area to intensify their productivity and income with improvements in TE. Different socioeconomic variables were observed to be negatively related to technical inefficiency. Ensuring the availability of quality DOC and feed, vaccination service, tax exemption, subsidy, poultry insurance with an all-out poultry-friendly policy are the needs of the current situation.

Introduction

Government efforts, the involvement of some NGOs and entrepreneurs, and changes in the socioeconomic status of the country over the most recent two to three decades have favored the greater investment shift in the Bangladeshi poultry sector (Raha, 2013). Poultry farm in Bangladesh has changed a lot of people's fate and this is all about the entrepreneurs how to start a poultry farm and serve the nation. Entrepreneurship development is a precondition for the sustained economic development of a country (Enke, 1978, p. 538), and poultry can play a vital role in this regard.

One of the vital challenges of Bangladesh's agriculture is its capability to nourish the ever-increasing population with nutritious food. Poultry industry is one of the chief sources of cheap, good quality, nutritious animal protein (Shamsuddoha, 2010). Poultry farming is a sub-sector of the agricultural sector in Bangladesh. By far, poultry is the chief among the livestock sub-sectors containing generally of chickens, ducks and turkeys (FAO, 2009). In total, poultry

* Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Bangladesh University of Business and Technology (BUBT), Dhaka 1216, Bangladesh. E-mail: mhsnju@gmail.com

products (egg and meat) constitute 30% of all animal protein consumed worldwide (Permin *et al.*, 2003). In global meat production, poultry meat is in the second place after pork (FAO, 2007).

According to the Department of Livestock (DLS), about 6.5% of national GDP of Bangladesh is accounted for by its livestock sector (Banglapedia). According to Bangladesh Poultry Industries Coordination Committee (BPICC) annual growth rate of poultry is 15-18%, and its contribution to GDP is 2.4% (Dhaka Tribune, March 10, 2019). About 38% of animal protein originates from poultry meat and egg (BLRI, 2010). Table 1 shows the contribution of sub-sectors of the agricultural sector to GDP at a constant (2005-06) price. Although the share of the agriculture sector in GDP is declining in relative terms, its share has increased considerably in absolute terms. In the Financial Year (FY) 2015-16, the role of agriculture was forecasted to be 11.67%. Further, the growth rate of all sub-sectors dropped during 2015-16 as compared to the previous year.

Sub-Sector	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16*
Crop	10.88	10.63	10.79	10.5	10.01	9.49	9.28	8.87	8.32
Livestock	2.19	2.13	2.06	1.98	1.9	1.84	1.78	1.73	1.66
Forestry	1.82	1.82	1.81	1.79	1.78	1.76	1.74	1.72	1.69
Total	14.89	14.58	14.66	14.27	13.69	13.09	12.8	12.32	11.67
Fisheries	3.79	3.78	3.73	3.73	3.68	3.68	3.69	3.69	3.65
Note: * implies forecasted value.									
<i>Source: Bangladesh Economic Review, 2016, Table 2.4, p. 21</i>									

The measurement of farm efficiency is a central area of research both in the developed and developing world (Binuomote *et al.*, 2008). The analysis of efficiency is generally associated with the possibility of farms producing a certain optimal level of output from a given level of resources or certain level of output at least cost (Battese and Coelli, 1995; and Parikh and Shah, 1995). Technical Efficiency (TE) represents the ability of firms to hire the 'best practice' in an industry so that not more than the required amount of a given set of inputs is used in producing the 'best' level of output (Ajibefun *et al.*, 2002; and Ohajianya *et al.*, 2006). Against this backdrop, the present study aims to estimate the determinants of: (i) poultry layer farms output, and (ii) TE of table poultry layer farms in Bangladesh.

Two approaches are mainly used to estimate TE, i.e., parametric and nonparametric. The parametric approach includes Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA), while nonparametric approach includes the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method. DEA is known to be sensitive to outliers (Hasnain *et al.*, 2015). The main disadvantage of employing this mathematical technique is that it does not take into account other sources of statistical noise

besides the inefficiency (Coelli *et al.*, 2005). For that reason, this study uses the parametric technique, SFA. Parametric approach takes into account the stochastic noises of the data, whereas the DEA assumes that there is no stochastic noise in the data (Abedullah and Mustaq, 2007). The rest of the paper is structured as follows: it reviews the literature, followed by a description of the data and methodology used in the study. Subsequently, it discusses the results obtained, and finally, it offers the conclusion with some suggestions.

Literature Review

A good number of studies have been undertaken on different aspects of poultry farming in Bangladesh. The studies include production performance of poultry and demand for poultry (Ukil and Paul, 1994; Islam and Nabiul, 2001; Khan *et al.*, 2006; Rahman *et al.*, 2009; Talukder *et al.*, 2010; and Shah *et al.*, 2011), measuring relative costs, returns and economic analyses (Miah, 1990; Ahmed *et al.*, 1995, Bhuiyan, 2003; Alam, 2004; and Islam *et al.*, 2016), benefit and profitability analysis of contract farming (Vukina and Poster, 1996; Bairagi, 2004; Begum and Alam, 2005; and Jabbar *et al.*, 2007), effectiveness of trained farmers (Ershad *et al.*, 2004), marketing and value chain analysis (Rahman *et al.*, 2004; and USAID-ATDP, 2005), role of NGO in poultry (Ahmed, 2001; and Shamsuddoha, 2009), role of poultry in biogas and electricity generation (Zaman, 2007; Alam *et al.*, 2014; and Sajib *et al.*, 2015), and environmental impact of the poultry sector in Bangladesh (Akter *et al.*, 2004).

However, these studies were quite descriptive in nature and suffered from lack of economic judgmental analysis. The major effort of most of the previous works in Bangladesh was on the production, marketing and distribution aspect of poultry and such type of studies employed mainly simple cost-benefit analysis. There have been some studies that have examined the efficiency of agricultural production of major food crops like rice, wheat, fish, maize, etc. in Bangladesh based on SFA and DEA (Wadud and White, 2000; Kamruzzaman *et al.*, 2006; Haider *et al.*, 2011; and Uddin *et al.*, 2017). However, no studies have dealt with the poultry sector. The efficiency analyses of poultry that have been done earlier (Sarker *et al.*, 1999; and Effiong and Onyenweaku, 2006) were not based on any econometrical or statistical tools.

Hassan (2018) had analyzed the TE of poultry broiler production in Bangladesh using a sample of 100 poultry farmers selected from Savar and Dhamrai Upazilla using stochastic parametric technique. However, the present study differs from the previous study by introducing the concept of efficiency considering variables that relate to both individual aspects and aspects related to the decision-making process of the farmer in the form of well-known production function and stochastic analysis which makes this paper unique.

Objective

The main objective of the study is to estimate the determinants of: (i) poultry layer farms output, and (ii) TE of poultry layer farms in Bangladesh.

Data and Methodology

For the study, Dhamrai and Savar Upazilla under Dhaka district and Kuliarchar and Bajitpur Upazilla under Kishoreganj district in Bangladesh were selected. Both primary and secondary data were used. The primary data was collected from the poultry farmers through a structured questionnaire (see Appendix). The study also obtained information from different issues of *Bangladesh Statistical Year Book*, *Bangladesh Economic Review* and *Farm Poultry and Livestock Survey 2007-08*". About 110 layer farmers were studied, and after necessary correction, 100 poultry farmers were finalized for the study. The farmers were randomly selected, i.e., 50 farmers from Kishoreganj and 50 from Dhaka. The farms were categorized according to the number of birds reared in the farm as followed by Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS) (Table 2).

No. of Birds	Categories of Farms
Up to 1,000	Small
1,001-5,000	Medium
Above 5,000	Large

Source: "Farm Poultry and Livestock Survey 2007-08" by Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics

The Analytical Framework

A production function is the functional relationship describing the maximum output that can be produced from a specific set of inputs, given the existing technology available to the firms involved.

A stochastic production function is defined as:

$$Y_i = F(X_i, B) \exp(V_i - U_i), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad \dots(1)$$

where Y_i is output of the i^{th} farm, X_i is the vector of input quantities used by the i^{th} farm, B is the vector of unknown parameters to be estimated, $f(\cdot)$ represents an appropriate function (e.g., Cobb-Douglas, translog, etc.). The term V_i is a symmetric error, which accounts for random variations in output due to factors beyond the control of the farmer, e.g., weather, disease outbreaks, measurement errors, etc., while the term U_i is a non-negative random variable representing inefficiency in production relative to the stochastic frontier. The random error V_i is expected to be independently and identically dispersed. The stochastic frontier model was independently proposed by Aigner *et al.* (1977) and Meeusen and Broeck (1977).

According to Battese and Coelli (1995), technical inefficiency effect is defined as:

$$U_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_i Z_i + W_i$$

where Z_i is a vector of explanatory variables associated with the technical inefficiency effects. δ_i is the vector of unknown parameter to be estimated, W_i is unobservable random variables,

which are assumed to be identically distributed, obtained by truncation of the normal distribution with mean zero and unknown variance σ^2 , such that u_i is non-negative. Stata 14 was applied to run the stochastic frontier model.

The Empirical Model

For this study, the production technology of poultry farmers was assumed to be specified by the Cobb-Douglas frontier production function defined as follows:

$$Y = aX_1^{\beta_1} X_2^{\beta_2} X_3^{\beta_3} X_4^{\beta_4} X_5^{\beta_5} X_6^{\beta_6} X_7^{\beta_7} e^{V_i - U_i} \quad \dots(2)$$

$$Y = f(X_a; B_i)e^E$$

where

- Y = Quantity of eggs produced
- X_a = A vector of input and other explanatory variable quantities
- B_i = A vector of unknown parameter to be estimated
- e = Error term
- E = Stochastic disturbance term consisting of two independent elements which are U_i and V_i , where by $E = U_i + V_i$
- U_i = One-sided efficiency component with a half normal distribution.
- V_i = The non-negative unobservable random variables associated with the technical efficiency of egg production.

The random error E represents random variations in the economic environment facing the production units, reflecting chances such as weather, disease outbreak, variable input quality, measurement errors, and omitted variables from the functional form (Aigner *et al.*, 1977).

Cobb-Douglas production function model can be estimated using Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method, in a linear form. The estimated equation is:

$$\ln Y_i = \ln a + \beta_1 \ln X_{1i} + \beta_2 \ln X_{2i} + \beta_3 \ln X_{3i} + \beta_4 \ln X_{4i} + \beta_5 \ln X_{5i} + \varepsilon_i \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\ln Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_{1i} + \beta_2 \ln X_{2i} + \beta_3 \ln X_{3i} + \beta_4 \ln X_{4i} + \beta_5 \ln X_{5i} + \varepsilon_i \quad \dots(4)$$

where

- $\ln$ = the natural logarithm to base e
- Y_i = Output of the poultry egg per batch
- X_1 = Number of days worked in a year
- X_2 = Size of DOC (Day Old Chicks), i.e., number of birds per batch
- X_3 = Cost of feed per batch (in taka)
- X_4 = Value of capital (in taka)
- X_5 = Farm area measured in decimal (1 Decimal = 435.6 or 436 sq.ft.)

$$\varepsilon_i = V_i - U_i; \quad i = 1, \dots, N$$

v_i = random errors for farm i

U_i = Technical efficiency effect which is the result of behavior factors that could be controlled by an efficient management. It denotes the specific technical efficiency factor for farm i .

β_0 = Intercept

β coefficients are unknown parameters to be estimated, by the method of maximum likelihood, using the econometric package Stata version 14.

Measuring Inefficiency Determinants

U_i for layer farm can be expressed as:

$$U_i = Z_0 + \delta_1 \ln Z_1 + \delta_2 \ln Z_2 + \delta_3 \ln Z_3 + \delta_4 \ln Z_4 + \delta_5 \ln Z_5 + \delta_6 \ln Z_6 + \delta_7 \ln Z_7 + \delta_8 \ln Z_8 + \delta_9 \ln Z_9 + \delta_{10} Z_{10} + \delta_{11} Z_{11} + \delta_{12} Z_{12} + \delta_{13} \ln Z_{13} + \delta_{14} \ln Z_{14} + W_i \quad \dots(5)$$

where

U_i = Economic efficiency of the i^{th} farmer (or the deviation from maximum potential output attributable to resource use efficiency)

Z_1 = Years of farming experience in poultry production of the i^{th} farmer

Z_2 = Age of the farmers (in years)

Z_3 = Level of formal education (years of schooling)

Z_4 = Household size (family members in number)

Z_5 = Training on poultry (if Yes = 1; No = 0)

Z_6 = Access to credit facility (if Yes = 1; No = 0)

Z_7 = Meetings with extension agents/respective government agencies per poultry production season (Yes = 1; No = 0)

Z_8 = Location of farm (Urban = 1; Rural = 0)

Z_9 = Types of poultry occupation

(1 = Poultry as main occupation and no other job

0 = Poultry as part-time occupation and involved in other jobs also)

Z_{10} = Marital status (Married = 1; Unmarried = 0)

Z_{11} = Membership of farmers association/cooperative society (Yes = 1; No = 0)

Z_{12} = Ownership of the farm (Partnership = 1, Sole proprietor = 0)

Z_{13} = Gender (Female = 1; Male = 0)

Z_{14} = Regular medication/Vaccination facilities (Yes = 1; No = 0)

$Z_0 = \text{Constant}$

$W_i = \text{Unobservable random variables}$

To determine the contributing factors to the observed technical efficiency, the above model was formulated and the δ coefficients are the unknown parameters to be estimated.

Hypothesis Testing

The multiple regression models are used to test different hypotheses based on a priori assumptions. The multiple regression model tests a null hypothesis H_0 against an alternative hypothesis H_1 as follows:

$$H_0: \beta_i's = 0$$

$$H_1: \beta_i's \neq 0; (i = 1, 2, \dots, 6)$$

The null hypothesis for the multiple model states that none of the independent variables had any effect on the output of eggs. The alternative hypothesis states that at least one of the factors contributes to the output of eggs.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

It is observed from Table 3 that in the study area, the mean flock size was 2,436 birds, the average experience of layer farmers was 11.4 years, the average age of layer farmers was 42 years, and the average number of family members of the poultry farmers was 5.

Variable	Obs.	Mean	SD	Min.	Max.
Flock Size	100	2435.8	2497.306	70	8500
Experience	100	11.423	5.494681	1	24
Age	100	42.05	9.020039	23	63
Family Members	100	5.00	1.687745	0	8

Stochastic Frontier Production Function for Layer Farm

The estimates for parameters of the Cobb-Douglas production function represent percentage change in the dependent variable as a result of percentage change in the independent variables, and as such show the relative position of these variables to poultry productivity.

Frontier Function for Layer Small Farm

Labor input ($\ln X_1$) measured as man per days affects poultry production positively and was observed to be significant at 5% level in the study area (Table 4). Poultry production is labor-intensive, and the more attention the farmers paid to the birds, the more is the poultry output. Thus, 0.08 elasticity of labor suggests that a 1% increase in labor use would result in an 0.08% increase in the farm output, given that other inputs are constant. DOC size ($\ln X_2$) is positive as

Table 4: Results of Cobb-Douglas Production Function for Layer Small Farm				
Number of Obs.		=	39	
$F(5, 33)$		=	27.97	$R^2 = 0.809$
Prob > F		=	0.000	Adj. $R^2 = 0.780$
Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	$P > t$
$\ln X_1$	0.089	0.038	2.322	0.025
$\ln X_2$	0.257	0.058	4.369	9.571E-05
$\ln X_3$	0.278	0.050	5.554	2.76E-06
$\ln X_4$	0.113	0.034	3.321	0.004
$\ln X_5$	0.060	0.026	2.308	0.027
_cons	1.021	0.507	2.011	0.042
RTS	0.799			
Note: $\ln X_1$ = Labor Input; $\ln X_2$ = DOC Size; $\ln X_3$ = Feed Input; $\ln X_4$ = Capital Input; and $\ln X_5$ = Area of Farm. Dependent Variable: $\ln Y_{egg}$				

expected and significant at 1% level. This means that farmers who stock higher number of birds produce more than those with lesser number of birds. The coefficient of 0.25 implies that 1% increase in the number of DOC will result in a 0.25% increase in the number of layers produced per cycle given that other inputs are constant. The estimated coefficient of feed input ($\ln X_3$) was positive and significant at 1% level. Feed appeared to be the most vital production factor with the elasticity of 0.27. This was in agreement with the concept of weight gain in layer production. Capital input ($\ln X_4$) variable was also significant and positive in sign. As more capital is invested in the poultry business, there is increased poultry production by farmers. Thus, the 0.11 elasticity of feed suggests that a 1% increase in feed inputs, would result in an increase of 0.11% in the farm output. Finally, the estimated coefficient for farm area ($\ln X_5$) measured in decimal was positive and significant at 5% level. Output of poultry majorly depends on farm size. Therefore, the 0.06 elasticity of farm size implies that a 1% increase in farm size, ceteris paribus, would lead to an increase of 0.06% in the output of poultry layer farmers.

Frontier Function for Layer Medium Farm

As observed from Table 5, all the variables in this case have positive coefficients, implying that an increase in any variable would lead to an increase in egg production.

Frontier Function for Layer Large Farm

Table 6 shows the output elasticity of variables in the case of layer large farms. In this case, similar result as before is obtained. All the variables affect the output positively and all are significant at either 5% or 1% level.

Table 5: Results of Cobb-Douglas Production Function for Layer Medium Farm				
Number of Obs.		=	34	
$F(5, 28)$		=	17.87	$R^2 = 0.761$
Prob > F		=	0.00001	Adj $R^2 = 0.718$
Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	$P > t$
$\ln X_1$	0.106	0.026	4.001	0.000
$\ln X_2$	0.264	0.077	3.402	0.001
$\ln X_3$	0.289	0.062	4.644	0.000
$\ln X_4$	0.101	0.050	2.027	0.049
$\ln X_5$	0.060	0.027	2.240	0.034
_cons	-1.000	0.268	-3.729	0.000
RTS	0.821			

Table 6: Results of Cobb-Douglas Production Function for Layer Large Farm				
Number of Obs.		=	27	
$F(5, 21)$		=	9.34	$R^2 = 0.699$
Prob > F		=	0.000	Adj $R^2 = 0.616$
Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	$P > t$
$\ln X_1$	0.110	0.029	3.725	0.000
$\ln X_2$	0.270	0.065	4.116	0.000
$\ln X_3$	0.290	0.105	2.766	0.010
$\ln X_4$	0.100	0.041	2.417	0.023
$\ln X_5$	0.070	0.016	4.335	0.000
_cons	1.030	0.477	2.155	0.041
RTS	0.843			

Determinants of Technical Efficiency

Inefficiency Determinants for Layer Small Farm

Table 7 shows a negative sign for most of the variables. All these parameter estimates were significantly different from zero. The negative sign on these variables implies that an increase in these variables decreases technical deficiency conversely increasing TE.

Variable	Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Err.	Z	$P[Z > z]$
Farming experience in poultry production (in years)	Z_1	-0.287	0.119	-2.414	0.015
Age of the farmers	Z_2	-0.141	0.053	-2.653	0.008
Level of education	Z_3	-0.299	0.149	-1.995	0.046
Family size	Z_4	-0.490	0.151	-3.241	0.001
Training on poultry	Z_5	-0.330	0.165	-2.003	0.045
Access to credit facility	Z_6	-0.255	0.078	-3.273	0.001
Meeting with extension agent/govt. agency	Z_7	-0.195	0.089	-2.200	0.027
Location of farm	Z_8	-0.033	0.011	-2.984	0.002
Types of poultry occupation	Z_9	-0.005	0.007	-0.661	0.508
Marital status	Z_{10}	-0.143	0.055	-2.571	0.010
Membership of farmers association/Cooperative society	Z_{11}	-0.011	0.017	-0.649	0.516
Ownership of the farm	Z_{12}	0.001	0.221	0.008	0.993
Gender	Z_{13}	-0.108	0.051	-2.115	0.034
Regular medication/Vaccination facilities	Z_{14}	-0.413	0.125	-3.306	0.000
Constant	Z_0	2.765	0.156	17.700	0.000
Diagnostic Statistics					
sigma ²		0.49	0.059	8.281	
gamma		0.588	0.300	1.959	
Log Likelihood		-13.991	2.758	-5.072	
Mean TE		0.34			
No. of Observations	39				

The estimated coefficient of farming experience variable (Z_1) is negative and significant at 0.01 significance level. This indicates that farmers with more years of farming experience in poultry production are relatively more efficient and vice versa. The more the farmers stay in poultry farming business, the more they get acquainted with the risk elements and ways of mitigating possible losses through them. Therefore, 0.28 elasticity of experience implies that a 1% increase in farming experience would result to an increase of 0.28% in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for age variable (Z_2) of the farmers is negative as expected and significant at 0.01 significance level. It is believed that the older the farmer, the more experienced he or she will be.

The estimated coefficient of education variable (Z_3) is negative and significant at 0.05 significance level. The implication is that poultry farmers with more years of schooling tend to be more efficient in poultry production. Farmers with higher education respond readily to

the use of improved technologies, thus producing closer to the frontier. Therefore, the elasticity of education of 0.29 suggests that a 1% increase in education would result in an 0.29% increase in farm output.

The estimated coefficient for family size variable (Z_4) is negative and statistically significant at 0.01 significance level. This indicates that farmers who have more family members in their household tend to be more efficient in poultry production. More adults among family members means more labor force and thus saving of labor cost. Therefore, elasticity of family size of 0.49 suggests that a 1% increase in family members would result in an 0.49% increase in farm output.

The estimated coefficient for training (Z_5) is negative and statistically significant at 0.05 significance level. This indicates that farmers who received training tend to be more efficient in poultry production. Therefore, an elasticity of training variable of 0.33 suggests that a 1% increase in training would result in an 0.33% increase in farm output.

The estimated coefficient for access to credit variable (Z_6) is negative and significant at 0.01 significance levels. This indicates that farmers who have greater access to credit, tend to be more efficient in poultry production. Availability of credit helps to increase the farm size and provide adequate production and maintenance inputs. Therefore, an elasticity of credit of 0.25 implies that a 1% increase in credit would result in an 0.25% increase in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for extension visits variable (Z_7) is negative and significant at 0.05 significance level. This indicates that farmers who had more extension visits and teachings, tend to be more efficient in poultry production. Extension visit is highly necessary in poultry farming because it provides the farmers the opportunity to learn new techniques of farming. Therefore, an elasticity of extension visit of 0.19 implies that a 1% increase in extension visit would result in an 0.19% increase in farm output.

The estimated coefficient for location variable (Z_8) is negative and significant at 0.05 significance level. The negative sign on the parameter for location implies that farms who were further away from the city or urban areas or are located in rural areas tend to have lower TE.

The estimated coefficient for poultry occupation (Z_9) is negative but not significant even at 0.05 significance level. This may be because the types of poultry occupation is not a matter of great concern. Poultry is an activity that can be conducted side-by-side with other agricultural or even non-agricultural work. Poultry production does not require full-time effort. This is an important reason for the rising popularity of poultry business among people.

The estimated coefficient of marital status variable (Z_{10}) is negative and significant at 0.05 significance level. Thus, married farmers tend to be more technically efficient, probably reflecting more availability of labor, which is consistent with larger families having more labor at their disposal, thus contributing to higher TE.

The estimated coefficient for membership of farmer's association (Z_{11}) is negative but insignificant. Though the negative sign on the parameter implies that membership of farmer's association might lower technical inefficiency, the result is not significant.

The estimated coefficient for ownership of the farm (Z_{12}) is positive but insignificant. Besides, the value of the estimated coefficient is also very negligible. Thus, types of ownership of the farm does not affect poultry efficiency.

The estimated coefficient for gender (Z_{13}) is negative and significant. The negative sign implies that female farmers tend to have higher technical efficiency than their male counterparts.

The estimated coefficient for regular medication input (Z_{14}) is negative and statistically significant at 0.01 significance level. Poultry production involves high-level risks because the birds are susceptible to various diseases and pests attack. To lessen these, drugs have to be given from time to time. Also certain drugs are needed to improve their growth and performance. So the appropriate amount of these drugs used determines the level of success and profitability in poultry business. Therefore, an elasticity of regular medication of 0.41 implies that a 1% increase in regular medication would result in an 0.41% increase in farm output.

Diagnostic Statistics

The value of sigma square is 0.49 and is highly significant. This result indicates a good fit and the exactness of the specified distribution hypothesis of the composite error term. Furthermore, a high value of the natural log for the likelihood functions (-13.99), which is always negative, implies that the observed results were more likely to occur, again implying a high predictive ability of the model. The value of gamma measures the relationship between random variation in the production of eggs and inefficiency in the use of inputs. The computed value of 0.588 implied that 59% of the random variation in layer production is explained by inefficiency in resource utilization. This implies that the OLS estimates will not be adequate to explain the inefficiencies of poultry layer farming. Hence, the specification of a stochastic frontier production function is therefore justified. The mean TE is 0.34 (34%) implying that the farmers are not fully efficient as the observed output is 66% less than the maximum possible output.

Inefficiency Determinants for Layer Medium Farm

It is observed from Table 8 that, except for the variable poultry occupation (Z_9), membership of association (Z_{11}), ownership of the farm (Z_{12}) and gender (Z_{13}), the estimated coefficient of farming experience (Z_1), age (Z_2), education (Z_3), family size (Z_4), training (Z_5), credit facility (Z_6), extension agent visit (Z_7), and farm location (Z_8) are negative and significant at 0.01 and 0.05 levels. The specialty of poultry farming is that it can be taken up on a part-time basis. It does not require full-time effort. Further, sole ownership or partnership both are suitable for poultry, and both males or females can take up poultry farming. So, insignificance of these variables does not matter much.

Diagnostic Statistics

The value of sigma square is 0.62 which is significant. This result indicates a good fit and the correctness of the specified distribution assumption of the composite error term. The computed value of gamma (0.678) implies that 68% of the random variation in production

Table 8: Estimated Determinants of Technical Inefficiency for Layer Medium Farm					
Variable	Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Err.	Z	$P[Z > z]$
Farming experience in poultry production (in years)	Z_1	-0.248	0.090	-2.743	0.006
Age of the farmers	Z_2	-0.170	0.055	-3.044	0.002
Level of education	Z_3	-0.359	0.094	-3.787	1.57E-04
Family size	Z_4	-0.411	0.138	-2.976	0.002
Training on poultry	Z_5	-0.388	0.111	-3.496	0.000
Access to credit facility	Z_6	-0.238	0.122	-1.955	0.051
Meeting with extension agent/govt. agency	Z_7	-0.101	0.051	-1.992	0.046
Location of farm	Z_8	-0.099	0.048	-2.031	0.035
Types of poultry occupation	Z_9	-0.008	0.005	-1.481	0.138
Marital status	Z_{10}	-0.088	0.045	-1.935	0.053
Membership of farmers association/Cooperative society	Z_{11}	-0.036	0.025	-1.426	0.155
Ownership of the farm	Z_{12}	0.006	0.014	0.474	0.638
Gender	Z_{13}	-0.04	0.021	-1.895	0.635
Regular medication/Vaccination facilities	Z_{14}	-0.446	0.172	-2.593	0.005
Constant	Z_0	0.943	0.156	6.036	0.000
Diagnostic Statistics					
sigma ²		0.62	0.078	7.931	
gamma		0.678	0.310	2.186	
Log Likelihood		-18.801	1.118	-16.81	
Mean TE		0.48			
No. of Observations	34				

is explained by inefficiency in resource utilization. The mean TE is 0.48 (48%), implying that the farmers are not fully efficient as the observed output is 52% less than the maximum possible output.

Inefficiency Determinants for Layer Large Farm

It is observed from Table 9 that in the case of large farms, except variables Z_9 , Z_{11} and Z_{12} (poultry occupation, membership of association, and ownership respectively), the estimated coefficients of all other variables are negative and significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level.

Diagnostic Statistics

The value of sigma square is 0.68, which is significant. This result indicates a good fit and the correctness of the specified distribution assumption of the composite error term. The computed value of gamma (0.79) implies that 79% of the random variation in production is explained by inefficiency in resource utilization. The mean TE is 0.61 (61%), implying that the farmers are not fully efficient as the observed output is 39% less than the maximum possible output.

Table 9: Estimated Determinants of Technical Inefficiency for Layer Large Farm					
Variable	Para-meter	Coefficient	Std. Err.	Z	$P[Z > z]$
Farming experience in poultry production (in years)	Z_1	-0.377	0.116	-3.248	0.001
Age of the farmers	Z_2	-0.182	0.089	-2.045	0.045
Level of education	Z_3	-0.400	0.141	-2.835	0.004
Family size	Z_4	-0.388	0.196	-1.975	0.048
Training on poultry	Z_5	-0.408	0.177	-2.308	0.021
Access to credit facility	Z_6	-0.270	0.099	-2.731	0.006
Meeting with extension agent/govt. agency	Z_7	-0.120	0.051	-2.358	0.018
Location of farm	Z_8	-0.120	0.054	-2.216	0.028
Types of poultry occupation	Z_9	-0.012	0.008	-1.397	0.164
Marital status	Z_{10}	-0.100	0.041	-2.408	0.016
Membership of farmers association/Cooperative society	Z_{11}	-0.020	0.015	-1.313	0.193
Ownership of the farm	Z_{12}	0.007	0.009	0.86	0.389
Gender	Z_{13}	-0.05	0.030	-1.655	0.098
Regular medication/Vaccination facilities	Z_{14}	-0.508	0.113	-4.464	0.000
Constant	Z_0	2.001	0.156	12.809	0.000
Diagnostic Statistics					
sigma ²		0.68		0.04917	13.829
gamma		0.795		0.268354	2.962
Log Likelihood		-28.281		1.428129	-19.802
Mean TE		0.61			
No. of Observations	27				

The findings confirm that there is much potential for improving the performance of layer egg production and hence the net returns that farmers obtain from their capital and labor investment by improving the TE.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing results are presented in Table 10.

H_{01} which specifies that the inefficiency effects are not stochastic, was strongly rejected.

H_{02} which states that the inefficiency effects are absent from the model, was rejected at 1% level, which implies that inefficiency exists in the model.

H_{03} which specifies that the explanatory variables in the model measuring the inefficiency have zero coefficients, was rejected as well at 1% level. This implies that the explanatory variables contributed significantly to the explanation of inefficiency in poultry egg production in the sample area.

Table 10: Hypothesis Testing Results					
S. No.	Hypothesis	Likelihood Ratio	χ^2	p-Value	Decision
1.	$H_{01}: \gamma = 0$	47.79	17.71	0.001	Reject H_{01}
2.	No inefficiency effect [$H_{02}: Z_0 = Z_1 = Z_2 = Z_3 = Z_4 = \dots = Z_{14} = 0$] Inefficiency effects in the stochastic production function are not stochastic.	35.51	25.73	3.6E-05	Reject H_{02}
3.	No effects of inefficiency factors included in the inefficiency model [$H_{03}: \delta_1 + \delta_2 + \delta_3 + \dots + \delta_{14} = 0$]	29.858	19.89	0.000	Reject H_{03}
4.	$H_{04}: \mu = 0$	31.58	27.33	1.7E-05	Reject H_{04}

Finally, H_{04} which states that each farm was operating on the technically efficient frontier and that the systematic and random efficiency in the inefficiency effects are zero, was rejected in favor of the presence of inefficiency effects.

Conclusion

In this study, technical inefficiency of poultry farms of Bangladesh was estimated by using the stochastic frontier method. The results of the study provide insight for policy makers on how to make better efforts to improve poultry farm efficiency. From the study, it is observed that large farms are more technically efficient than medium farms and medium farms are more efficient than small farms. This supports the theory that large farms exhibit many types of economies such as economies of scale, economies of management and operation and economies of buying (inputs) and selling (output). Due to the least per unit cost, reduced managerial cost in long run, large farms face more efficiency than medium and small farms. Conversely, the smaller the farm, the lesser the efficiency (at least as per as the present study). The smallholder broiler farmers are characterized by poor production process and low production quantities, thus slow growth. That is why small farms (and medium farms also) demand special nursing and policy support from the government to improve their efficiency.

The long-term position of Bangladesh as a prominent producer of poultry products seems strong, despite the bird flu epidemic that threatened to limit its prospect. The swelling demand for poultry meat and eggs has improved poultry activity into a full-grown industry from a mere household activity until recently. The poultry industry has immense potential for boosting the economic growth of the country as well as ensuring food security. Furthermore, it plays a pivotal role in the rural employment as maximum households are directly involved in livestock farming. Agricultural land is limited and is reducing day by day. A solution to the issue of farm land depletion could be formulation of a sensible and realistic land-use policy. Poultry is most probably the only sector that can grow vertically and produce maximum

amount of eggs and chicken meat using the minimum land. Rising population and moderate growth of per capita income, urbanization and high income elasticity of demand, are likely to bring an enormous increase in the demand for poultry products. It is high time for the Government of Bangladesh to take all necessary policy steps to promote entrepreneurship by enhancing the poultry sector particularly, by emphasizing the availability of quality chicks and feed, vaccination service of livestock, tax exemption, subsidy, poultry insurance, and finally creating a poultry-friendly environment.©

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Appendix

Poultry Farm Survey

Section 1: Identification of Sample Farm

Name of the Farm: _____

Date of Interview: _____

Address of the Farm:

a. District: _____

b. *Upazilla/Thana*: _____

c. Village/*Mohallah*: _____

d. Telephone No.: _____

e. Description of Main Activity: _____

f. Name and Designation of Respondent: _____

Section 2: General Information of the Farm:

1. Year of starting activities: _____

2. Type of the farm:

Broiler

Layer

Both

3. Size of the farm (flock size):

Small

Medium

Large

4. Ownership of the farm:

Sole proprietor

Partnership

Others

5. Starting capital/Amount of money invested: _____

Appendix (Cont.)

Section 3: Access to Infrastructure Facilities

1. Do you have any loan for farm?
 - Yes
 - No
2. If YES in 1, total amount of loan (at what percentage?): _____
3. What is the source of your loan?
 - NGO
 - Bank
 - Grameen Bank
 - Moneylenders
 - Others
4. What type of loan is easy to get?
 - Public
 - Private
 - Others
5. Why do you choose public/private sectors as loan source?
 - Easy to get/Available at any time
 - Easy and long-term installment
 - Very near from the farm
 - Requires less/almost no formalities
 - Others
6. Taxes and other payments for complete year
 1. Taxes paid (specify) _____ Amount taka _____
 2. Insurance taka (if available) _____
7. Others (specify) _____

Appendix (Cont.)

Questions to measure the sources of inefficiency:

Section 4: Socioeconomic Characteristics:

1. Year of farming experience in poultry production of the i^{th} farmer (in years):

- 0-2
- 3-6
- 7-10
- More than 10

2. Age of the i^{th} farmer (in years)

- 21-30
- 31-40
- 41-50
- Above 50

3. Highest level of education

- No Formal Education
- Read and Write Only
- Quranic Education
- Primary School Education
- Secondary School Education
- Tertiary Education

4. Family size (number of people dependent on you for living):

- 1-2
- 3-5
- 6-8
- Above 8

4.1 Number of adult and child

1. Adults _____ 2. Children _____

Appendix (Cont.)

5. Sex:

- Male
- Female

6. Marital status:

- Married
- unmarried

7. Land possessed by the farmers:

- Landless (0.0-0.5 acres)
- Small (0.51-2.5 acres)
- Medium (2.51-7.5 acres)
- Large (7.51+ acres)

8. Do you have access to credit?

- Yes
- No

9. If yes in 8, what are the sources of your credit?

- Commercial banks
- Agricultural cooperative and rural development bank
- Cooperative societies
- Moneylenders
- Friends and family
- Personal savings
- Others _____

10. Have you ever been visited by an extension agent?

- Yes
- No

Appendix (Cont.)

11. Have you taken any training on poultry production?

Yes

No

12. If YES in 11, from where?

NGO

Experienced Farmer

Government Youth Institution

Others

Questions related to measure the production function for meat/eggs (average and marginal productivity, returns to scale)

Section 5: Operational Cost of the Farm

(i) Working Capital (Last Production Cycle):

Name of Items	Quantity	Price per Unit (tk)	Total Cost (tk)
Day Old Broiler Chick			
Day Old Layer Chick			
Feed			
Vaccines			
Disinfection			
Utilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electricity: • Water: • Kerosene: • Petrol/Diesel: 			
Litter material			
Transport			
Night-Time Security			
Others			

Appendix (Cont.)

(ii) Cost of Capital and Equipment (Fixed Cost):

Name of Items	Quantity	Purchase Value/Cost (in taka)	Salvage Value (in taka)	Useful Life (or Cycles of Production) (in taka)	Depreciation Cost (in taka)	Replacement Cost (in taka) Replacing New One in Place of Old One
Cages (in case of layer only)						
Drinkers						
Feeders						
Building/Housing						
Rents						
Generator						
Brooder/Stoves						
Curtain						
Fan						
Tube Well						
Egg Trays						
Others: (Shovels, Buckets, Bowls, Rakes, etc.)						

Appendix (Cont.)

(iii) Labor Used:									
A. Hired Labor (Last Production Cycle)									
Operation	Adult Male		Adult Female		Children		Cost (tk)	Mode of Payment	Cost (tk)
	No. of Persons	Mode of Payment	No. of Persons	Mode of Payment	No. of Persons	Mode of Payment			
Drugs Administration, Vaccination									
Sweeping/Cleaning									
Feeding									
Egg Collection									
Record Keeping									
Others									

B. Family Labor (Last Production Cycle)									
Operation	Adult Male		Adult Female		Children		Cost (tk)	Mode of Payment	Cost (tk)
	No. of Persons	Mode of Payment	No. of Persons	Mode of Payment	No. of Persons	Mode of Payment			
Drugs Administration, Vaccination									
Sweeping/Cleaning									
Feeding									
Egg Collection									
Record Keeping									
Others									

Appendix (Cont.)

Section 6: Information on Value of Output:

1. How many cycles of production per year/Number of batches in a year?

Broiler: _____

Layer: _____

Flock Size (Last Production Batch): _____

i. Revenue from Meat Sales (at the end of each batch)/Value of Meat									
No. of Birds (Q) (1)	No. of Birds Consumed/ No. of Crates Consumed (2)	No. of Birds Given as Gift/No. of Crates Given as Gift (3)	Cost Per Bird (C) (in taka) (4)	Total Cost (TC) (in taka) (5)	No. of Birds Sold (per Crates =) (6)	Average Price (P) (in kg) (7)	Total Revenue (TR = PxQ*) (8)	Profit Ω = (TR - TC) (9)	Who are the buyers? If more than one buyer indicate (10)
No. of Birds (Stock of Bird)									
Mortality									

ii. Revenue from Egg Sales (at the end of each batch)/Value of Eggs										
Egg Sizes	Total Quantity Produced (Q) (1)	No. of Crates Consumed (2)	No. of Crates Given as Gift (3)	Cost(C) Per Bird (in taka) (4)	Total Cost (TC) (in taka) (5)	No. of Eggs Sold (N)/No. of Crates Sold (per crates =) (6)	Average Price Per Crate (7)	Total Revenue (TR = PxQ*) (8)	Profit Ω = (TR - TC) (9)	Who are the buyers? If more than one buyer indicate (10)
Large										
Medium										
Small										

Appendix (Cont.)

iii. Value of Aged/Exhausted Layers:

Aged/ Exhausted Layers	Number	Total Cost of Bird (in taka)	Price Per Bird	Total Revenue (TR = PxQ*)	Who are the buyers?
Sold					
Consumed					
Gift					

iv. Revenue from Sales of 'By-Products' of Poultry

By-Products	Quantity Sold	Price Per Unit (in taka)	Total Sale/ Revenue (in taka)	Who are the buyers?
Poultry manure/drooping (from layer specially)				
Empty bags of feed				
Empty containers of disinfectants				
Empty containers of drugs/vaccines				
Others				

Questions related to disclose the problems and challenges faced by the farmers:

Section 7: Constraint in Poultry-Meat/Egg Production:

- Not a problem at all = 0
- Not important problem = 1
- Important problem = 2
- Very important problem = 3

Appendix (Cont.)

S. No.	Constraints	Ratings	Coping Strategies from Respondent
1.	Inadequate capital		
2.	Feed		
3.	Drugs and vaccine		
4.	Labor		
5.	Water		
6.	Scarcity of raw materials for plants, furniture, buildings and equipment		
7.	Vulnerability to diseases and sensitivity to environmental factors		
8.	Poor quality of Day Old Chicks (DOC)		
9.	Marketing of products		
10.	Transport problem		
11.	Mortality problem		
12.	Lack of training facilities		
13.	Breakage of eggs in transit (in case of laying hens)		
14.	Political unrest		
15.	Bad road network		
16.	Government policy		

Appendix (Cont.)

Section 8: Factors Affecting Risk and Uncertainty in Poultry Business

1: Different sources of risks and uncertainties involved in poultry management in the study area:

Farming Risk Factors		Cost of Risk (in money terms)
High mortality/death rate		
Outbreak of diseases (Infestation of disease)		
Market risk	Changes in input prices	
	Output price fluctuation	
Political instability		
Diseases risk		
Lack of vaccine/If vaccine is not available		
Changes in weather/climate condition		
Cannibalism and feather pecking		
Breakage of egg/poor collection		
Attack by predator		
Power failure/Shortage of power supply		
Heat stress		
Untreated injury		
Unhygienic feed /Untreated drinking water		
Polluted litter		
Poor and inadequate finance		
Poor ventilation		
Poor roads and communication system		
Occurrence of natural disaster/calamities		

Appendix (Cont.)

2: Risk Management Practice:

Risk management practices adopted by the respondents in the study area.

Risk Management Practice	Use/Utilization			
	Never (0)	Rarely (1)	Often (2)	Always (3)
Proper and timely vaccination				
Fencing/Netting				
Disinfecting the poultry house				
Contract sales of poultry products				
Diversification (raising both layer and broilers)				
Pre-purchase of inputs				
Proper egg collection				
Good ventilation system				
Proper storage facilities				
Proper water and feed				
Proper financing				
Maintaining good hygiene				
Effective power supply				
Regular predator baiting				

Section 9: Marketing

1. Distance of the farm from the highway:
 - i. 0-3 mile ii. 4-7 mile
 - iii. 8-10 mile iv. Above 10 mile
2. Type of road to highway _____
3. Where do you sell?
 - i. The Farm ii. The Village Market
 - iii. Faria/Middlemen iv. Others (specify) _____
4. If the answer is (ii), then how do you reach there?
 - i. By Walking ii. By Bus
 - iii. By Rickshaw/Van iv. Others

Appendix (Cont.)

5. If the answer is (iii), list the reasons for selling to them.
 - i. Better price
 - ii. Only buyer available
 - iii. Marketing problem
 - iv. Avoiding price fluctuation
 - v. Others (specify)
6. In which months of the year there is high demand for your products and why?

7. Where do you get market information?
 - i. From traders
 - ii. From neighbors
 - iii. From friends and relatives
 - iv. Magazines
 - v. Others (specify) _____
8. How do you access this information? By
 - i. Physical visit
 - ii. Using telephone/mobile
 - iii. Asking traders who come to buy
 - iv. Listening to radios/Watching televisions
 - v. Others (specify) _____
9. Do you incur any cost to get that information?
 - i. Yes
 - ii. No
10. If yes in 9, how much (taka)? _____
11. Challenges and problems of poultry (chicken and egg) marketing in sample areas:

Different Marketing Problems	Intensity of Problem			
	Very Serious	Serious	Medium	Not a Problem at All
Unstable chicken prices				
Poor sales (demand seasonality), lower price in fasting and higher price in non-fasting time				
Lack of marketplace				
Poor infrastructure (road and market)				
Lack of information				
Poor infrastructure and lack of information				
Reliable markets very far				
Lack of buyers				

Appendix (Cont.)

Section 10: Use of Poultry and Poultry Technology

Are you able to adopt the following technology?

S. No.	Poultry Technology	Yes	No	If No, Why?
	Use of hybrid poultry			
	Sufficient use of water, feeder, litter			
	Temperature and light control in the house			
	Use of vaccination			
	Maintaining schedule of vaccination			
	Use of balanced diet			
	Disposal of litter and reuse of litter			
	Egg preservation system			

Section 11: Attitude Towards Poultry Production

S. No.	Statement	Agree	Slightly Agree	Disagree
1.	Concerned education is essential for poultry rearing.			
2.	University degree in poultry science is essential for poultry business.			
3.	For best income generation poultry may be a good industry.			
4.	Though <i>deshi</i> chicken meat is tasty, it is essential to rear exotic chicken higher in number.			
5.	Poultry is a suitable source of employment opportunity for women.			
6.	It is essential to vaccinate the livestock to prevent diseases.			
7.	Poultry farming is more profitable than paddy cultivation.			
8.	Poultry cum fish farming is more profitable than paddy cultivation.			

Appendix (Cont.)

Section 12: Litter Management of Poultry

How many tons of litter do you produce per batch? (in tons)

- Less than 100
- 101-200
- 201-400
- 401-600
- Over 600

1. Do you use

- All
- Some
- None of the litter

2. What percent of the litter you use for

- 2.1 Fertilizer ____
- 2.2 Feed? ____
- 2.3 Biogas Technology ____

3. Do you produce other livestock manures?

- Yes
- No

Section 13: Performance Measurement

Based on your experiences in running the business, please indicate your opinion regarding the following: 1. Strongly Disagree (SD), 2. Disagree (D), 3. Neutral (N), 4. Agree (A), and 5. Strongly Agree (SA).

Alternatives	SD	D	N	A	SA
I am satisfied with the growth of net income the poultry enterprise.					
Existing capital is sufficient to maintain and expand the business.					
I consider poultry business to be successful.					
I receive regular feedback both positive and negative.					
I have accessible alternatives of capital sources if needed.					
If needed, it is easy to get additional capital.					
I have access to information on capital sources.					
Have many helpful colleagues/friends who support the business.					
Distribution channel of my products is already in place.					
High cost of transportation.					
Lack of enough space for chicken and layer marketing in urban markets.					

Appendix (Cont.)

Please indicate your opinion regarding the importance of each factor in running your poultry business: 1. Very Insignificant (VI), 2. Insignificant (I), 3. Neutral (N), 4. Significant (S), and 5. Very Significant (VS).

Factor	VI	I	N	S	VS
Marketing					
Technology					
Capital access					
Social network					
Legal requirements					

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